

A Study on Intuitionistic Multi-Anti Fuzzy Subgroups

R.Muthuraj ¹, S.Balamurugan ²

¹PG and Research Department of Mathematics, H.H. The Rajah's College,
Pudukkotta 622 001, Tamilnadu, India.

²Department of Mathematics, Velammal College of Engineering & Technology,
Madurai-625 009, Tamilnadu, India.

ABSTRACT

For any intuitionistic multi-fuzzy set $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ of an universe set X , we study the set $[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ called the (α, β) -lower cut of A . It is the crisp multi-set $\{ x \in X : \mu_i(x) \leq \alpha_i, \nu_i(x) \geq \beta_i, \forall i \}$ of X . In this paper, an attempt has been made to study some algebraic structure of intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy subgroups and their properties with the help of their (α, β) -lower cut sets.

Keywords

Intuitionistic fuzzy set (IFS), Intuitionistic multi-fuzzy set (IMFS), Intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy subgroup (IMAFSG), Intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy normal subgroup (IMAFNSG), (\square, \square) -lower cut, Homomorphism.

Mathematics Subject Classification 20N25, 03E72, 08A72, 03F55, 06F35, 03G25, 08A05, 08A30.

1. INTRODUCTION

After the introduction of the concept of fuzzy set by Zadeh [14] several researches were conducted on the generalization of the notion of fuzzy set. The idea of Intuitionistic fuzzy set was given by Krassimir.T.Atanassov [1]. An Intuitionistic Fuzzy set is characterized by two functions expressing the degree of membership (belongingness) and the degree of non-membership (non-belongingness) of elements of the universe to the IFS. Among the various notions of higher-order fuzzy sets, Intuitionistic Fuzzy sets proposed by Atanassov provide a flexible framework to explain uncertainty and vagueness. An element of a multi-fuzzy set can occur more than once with possibly the same or different membership values. In this paper we study Intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy subgroup with the help of some properties of their (α, β) -lower cut sets. This paper is an attempt to combine the two concepts: Intuitionistic Fuzzy sets and Multi-fuzzy sets together by introducing two new concepts called Intuitionistic Multi-fuzzy sets and Intuitionistic Multi-Anti fuzzy subgroups.

2. PRELIMINARIES

In this section, we site the fundamental definitions that will be used in the sequel.

2.1 Definition [14]

Let X be a non-empty set. Then a **fuzzy set** $\mu : X \rightarrow [0,1]$.

2.2 Definition [9]

Let X be a non-empty set. A **multi-fuzzy set** A of X is defined as $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ where $\mu_A = (\mu_1, \mu_2, \dots, \mu_k)$, that is, $\mu_A(x) = (\mu_1(x), \mu_2(x), \dots, \mu_k(x))$ and $\mu_i : X \rightarrow [0,1]$, $\forall i=1,2,\dots,k$. Here k is the finite dimension of A . Also note that, for all i , $\mu_i(x)$ is a decreasingly ordered sequence of elements. That is, $\mu_1(x) \geq \mu_2(x) \geq \dots \geq \mu_k(x), \forall x \in X$.

2.3 Definition [1]

Let X be a non-empty set. An **Intuitionistic Fuzzy Set (IFS)** A of X is an object of the form $A = \{ \langle x, \mu(x), \nu(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$, where $\mu : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $\nu : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ define the degree of membership and the degree of non-membership of the element $x \in X$ respectively with $0 \leq \mu(x) + \nu(x) \leq 1, \forall x \in X$.

2.4 Remark [1]

- (i) Every fuzzy set A on a non-empty set X is obviously an intuitionistic fuzzy set having the form $A = \{ \langle x, \mu(x), 1-\mu(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$.
- (ii) In the definition 2.3, When $\mu(x) + \nu(x) = 1$, that is, when $\nu(x) = 1-\mu(x) = \mu^c(x)$, A is called fuzzy set.

2.5 Definition [13]

Let $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ where $\mu_A(x) = (\mu_1(x), \mu_2(x), \dots, \mu_k(x))$ and $\nu_A(x) = (\nu_1(x), \nu_2(x), \dots, \nu_k(x))$ such that $0 \leq \mu_i(x) + \nu_i(x) \leq 1$, for all $i, \forall x \in X$. Here, $\mu_1(x) \geq \mu_2(x) \geq \dots \geq \mu_k(x)$, $\forall x \in X$. That is, μ_i 's are decreasingly ordered sequence. That is, $0 \leq \mu_i(x) + \nu_i(x) \leq 1, \forall x \in X$, for $i=1, 2, \dots, k$. Then the set A is said to be an **Intuitionistic Multi-Fuzzy Set (IMFS)** with dimension k of X .

2.6 Remark [13]

Note that since we arrange the membership sequence in decreasing order, the corresponding non-membership sequence may not be in decreasing or increasing order.

2.7 Definition [13]

Let $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ and $B = \{ \langle x, \mu_B(x), \nu_B(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ be any two IMFS's having the same dimension k of X . Then

- (i) $A \subseteq B$ if and only if $\mu_A(x) \leq \mu_B(x)$ and $\nu_A(x) \geq \nu_B(x)$ for all $x \in X$.

- (ii) $A = B$ if and only if $\mu_A(x) = \mu_B(x)$ and $\nu_A(x) = \nu_B(x)$ for all $x \in X$.
- (iii) $\neg A = \{ \langle x, \nu_A(x), \mu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$
- (iv) $A \cap B = \{ \langle x, (\mu_{A \cap B})(x), (\nu_{A \cap B})(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$, where
 $(\mu_{A \cap B})(x) = \min\{ \mu_A(x), \mu_B(x) \} = (\min\{ \mu_{iA}(x), \mu_{iB}(x) \})_{i=1}^k$ and
 $(\nu_{A \cap B})(x) = \max\{ \nu_A(x), \nu_B(x) \} = (\max\{ \nu_{iA}(x), \nu_{iB}(x) \})_{i=1}^k$
- (v) $A \cup B = \{ \langle x, (\mu_{A \cup B})(x), (\nu_{A \cup B})(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$, where
 $(\mu_{A \cup B})(x) = \max\{ \mu_A(x), \mu_B(x) \} = (\max\{ \mu_{iA}(x), \mu_{iB}(x) \})_{i=1}^k$ and
 $(\nu_{A \cup B})(x) = \min\{ \nu_A(x), \nu_B(x) \} = (\min\{ \nu_{iA}(x), \nu_{iB}(x) \})_{i=1}^k$

Here $\{ \mu_{iA}(x), \mu_{iB}(x) \}$ represents the corresponding i^{th} position membership values of A and B respectively. Also $\{ \nu_{iA}(x), \nu_{iB}(x) \}$ represents the corresponding i^{th} position non-membership values of A and B respectively.

2.8 Theorem [13]

For any three IMFS's A, B and C , we have :

1. Commutative Law

$$A \cup B = B \cup A$$

$$A \cap B = B \cap A$$

2. Idempotent Law

$$A \cup A = A$$

$$A \cap A = A$$

3. De Morgan's Laws

$$\neg(A \cup B) = (\neg A \cap \neg B)$$

$$\neg(A \cap B) = (\neg A \cup \neg B)$$

4. Associative Law

$$A \cup (B \cap C) = (A \cup B) \cap C$$

$$A \cap (B \cup C) = (A \cap B) \cup C$$

5. Distributive Law

$$A \cup (B \cap C) = (A \cup B) \cap (A \cup C)$$

$$A \cap (B \cup C) = (A \cap B) \cup (A \cap C)$$

2.9 Definition

Let $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ be an IMFS and let $\alpha = (\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_k) \in [0, 1]^k$ and $\beta = (\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_k) \in [0, 1]^k$, where each $\alpha_i, \beta_i \in [0, 1]$ with $0 \leq \alpha_i + \beta_i \leq 1, \forall i$. Then (α, β) -lower cut of A is the set of all x such that $\mu_i(x) \leq \alpha_i$ with the corresponding $\nu_i(x) \geq \beta_i, \forall i$ and is denoted by $[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$. Clearly it is a crisp multi-set.

2.10 Definition

Let $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ be an IMFS and let $\alpha = (\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_k) \in [0, 1]^k$ and $\beta =$

$(\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_k) \in [0, 1]^k$, where each $\alpha_i, \beta_i \in [0, 1]$ with $0 \leq \alpha_i + \beta_i \leq 1, \forall i$. Then **strong (α, β) -lower cut** of A is the set of all x such that $\mu_i(x) < \alpha_i$ with the corresponding $\nu_i(x) > \beta_i, \forall i$ and is denoted by $[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)^*}$. Clearly it is also a crisp multi-set.

The following Theorem is an immediate consequence of the above definitions.

2.11 Theorem [13]

Let A and B are any two IMFS's of dimension k drawn from a set X . Then $A \subseteq B$ if and only if $[B]_{(\alpha, \beta)} \subseteq [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ for every $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]^k$ with $0 \leq \alpha_i + \beta_i \leq 1$ for all i .

2.12 Definition

An intuitionistic multi-fuzzy set (In short IMFS) $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in G \}$ of a group G is said to be an **intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy subgroup** of G (In short IMAFSG) if it satisfies the following : For all $x, y \in G$,

- (i) $\mu_A(xy) \leq \max \{ \mu_A(x), \mu_A(y) \}$
- (ii) $\mu_A(x^{-1}) = \mu_A(x)$
- (iii) $\nu_A(xy) \geq \min \{ \nu_A(x), \nu_A(y) \}$
- (iv) $\nu_A(x^{-1}) = \nu_A(x)$

2.13 Definition

An intuitionistic multi-fuzzy set (In short IMFS) $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in G \}$ of a group G is said to be an **intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy subgroup** of G (In short IMAFSG) if it satisfies :

- (i) $\mu_A(xy^{-1}) \leq \max \{ \mu_A(x), \mu_A(y) \}$ and
- (ii) $\nu_A(xy^{-1}) \geq \min \{ \nu_A(x), \nu_A(y) \}, \forall x, y \in G$

2.13.1 Remark

- (i) If A is an IFS of a group G , then we can not say about the complement of A , because it is not an IFS of G .
- (ii) If A is an IAFSG of a group G , then A^c is need not be an IFS of G .
- (iii) A is an IMAFSG of a group $G \Leftrightarrow$ each IFS $\{ \langle x, \mu_{iA}(x), \nu_{iA}(x) \rangle : x \in G \}_{i=1}^k$ is an IAFSG of G .
- (iv) If A is an IMAFSG of a group G , then in general, we can not say A^c is an IMFSG of the group G .

2.14 Definition

An IMAFSG $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in G \}$ of a group G is said to be an **intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy normal subgroup** (In short IMAFNNG) of G if it satisfies :

- (i) $\mu_A(xy) = \mu_A(yx)$ and
- (ii) $\nu_A(xy) = \nu_A(yx),$ for all $x, y \in G$

2.15 Theorem

An intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy subgroup (IMAFSG) A of a group G is said to be normal if it satisfies :

- (i) $\mu_A(g^{-1}xg) = \mu_A(x)$ and
- (ii) $\nu_A(g^{-1}xg) = \nu_A(x)$, for all $x \in A$ and $g \in G$

Proof Let $x \in A$ and $g \in G$ be any element.

Then $\mu_A(g^{-1}xg) = \mu_A(g^{-1}(xg)) = \mu_A((xg)g^{-1})$, since A is normal.
 $= \mu_A(x(gg^{-1})) = \mu_A(xe) = \mu_A(x)$. Hence the proof (i).

Now, $\nu_A(g^{-1}xg) = \nu_A(g^{-1}(xg)) = \nu_A((xg)g^{-1})$, since A is normal.
 $= \nu_A(x(gg^{-1})) = \nu_A(xe) = \nu_A(x)$. Hence the proof (ii).

2.16 Definition

Let (G, \cdot) be a groupoid and A, B be any two IMFS's having same dimension k of G . Then the **product** of A and B is denoted by $A \circ B$ and it is defined as :

$\forall x \in G, A \circ B(x) = (\mu_{A \circ B}(x), \nu_{A \circ B}(x))$ where

$$\mu_{A \circ B}(x) = \begin{cases} \max [\min \{ \mu_A(y), \mu_B(z) \} : yz=x, \forall y, z \in G] \\ 0_k = (0, 0, \dots, k \text{ times}), \text{ if } x \text{ is not expressible as } x=yz & \text{and} \\ \min [\max \{ \nu_A(y), \nu_B(z) \} : yz=x, \forall y, z \in G] \end{cases}$$

$$\nu_{A \circ B}(x) = \begin{cases} 1_k = (1, 1, \dots, k \text{ times}), \text{ if } x \text{ is not expressible as } x=yz \end{cases}$$

That is, $\forall x \in G,$

$$A \circ B(x) = \begin{cases} (\max[\min \{ \mu_A(y), \mu_B(z) \} : yz=x, \forall y, z \in G], \min[\max \{ \nu_A(y), \nu_B(z) \} : yz=x, \forall y, z \in G]) \\ (0_k, 1_k), \text{ if } x \text{ is not expressible as } x=yz \end{cases}$$

That is, $\forall x \in G,$

$$A \circ B(x) = \begin{cases} (\max[\min \{ \mu_{iA}(y), \mu_{iB}(z) \} : yz=x, \forall y, z \in G], \min[\max \{ \nu_{iA}(y), \nu_{iB}(z) \} : yz=x, \forall y, z \in G])_{i=1}^k \\ (0, 1)_k, \text{ if } x \text{ is not expressible as } x=yz \text{ where } (0, 1)_k = ((0, 1), (0, 1), \dots, k \text{ times}) \end{cases}$$

2.17 Definition

Let X and Y be any two non-empty sets and $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a mapping. Let A and B be any two IMFS's having same dimension k , of X and Y respectively. Then the **image** of $A(\subseteq X)$ under the map f is denoted by $f(A)$ and it is defined as :

$\forall y \in Y, f(A)(y) = (\mu_{f(A)}(y), \nu_{f(A)}(y))$ where

$$\mu_{f(A)}(y) = \begin{cases} \max\{\mu_A(x) : x \in f^{-1}(y)\} \\ 0_k, \text{ otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \text{and}$$

$$\nu_{f(A)}(y) = \begin{cases} \min\{\nu_A(x) : x \in f^{-1}(y)\} \\ 1_k, \text{ otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$\text{That is, } f(A)(y) = \begin{cases} (\max\{\mu_{iA}(x) : x \in f^{-1}(y)\}, \min\{\nu_{iA}(x) : x \in f^{-1}(y)\})_{i=1}^k \\ (0,1)_k, \text{ otherwise where } (0,1)_k = ((0,1), (0,1), \dots, k \text{ times}) \end{cases}$$

Also, the **pre-image** of $B(\subseteq Y)$ under the map f is denoted by $f^{-1}(B)$ and it is defined as :

$$\forall x \in X, f^{-1}(B)(x) = (\mu_B(f(x)), \nu_B(f(x)))$$

3. PROPERTIES OF (α, β) –LOWER CUT OF INTUITIONISTIC MULTI-FUZZY SET

In this section we shall prove some theorems on intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy subgroups of a group G with the help of their (α, β) –lower cuts.

3.1 Proposition

If A and B are any two IMFS's of a universal set X , then their (α, β) –lower cuts satisfies the following :

- (i) $[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)} \subseteq [A]_{(\delta, \theta)}$ if $\alpha \leq \delta$ and $\beta \geq \theta$
- (ii) $A \subseteq B$ implies $[B]_{(\alpha, \beta)} \subseteq [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$
- (iii) $[A \cap B]_{(\alpha, \beta)} = [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)} \cap [B]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$
- (iv) $[A \cup B]_{(\alpha, \beta)} \subseteq [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)} \cup [B]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ (Here equality holds if $\alpha_i + \beta_i = 1, \forall i$)
- (v) $[\cap A_i]_{(\alpha, \beta)} = \cap [A_i]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$, where $\alpha, \beta, \delta, \theta \in [0,1]^k$

3.2 Proposition

Let $(G, .)$ be a groupoid and A, B be any two IMFS's of G . Then we have $[A \circ B]_{(\alpha, \beta)} = [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)} [B]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ where $\alpha, \beta \in [0,1]^k$.

3.3 Theorem

If A is an intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy subgroup of a group G and $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]^k$, then the (α, β) -lower cut of A , $[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ is a subgroup of G , where $\mu_A(e) \leq \alpha$, $\nu_A(e) \geq \beta$ and 'e' is the identity element of G .

Proof since $\mu_A(e) \leq \alpha$ and $\nu_A(e) \geq \beta$, $e \in [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$. Therefore, $[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)} \neq \phi$.

Let $x, y \in [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$. Then $\mu_A(x) \leq \alpha$, $\nu_A(x) \geq \beta$ and $\mu_A(y) \leq \alpha$, $\nu_A(y) \geq \beta$.

Then $\forall i$, $\mu_{iA}(x) \leq \alpha_i$, $\nu_{iA}(x) \geq \beta_i$ and $\mu_{iA}(y) \leq \alpha_i$, $\nu_{iA}(y) \geq \beta_i$.

$$\Rightarrow \max\{\mu_{iA}(x), \mu_{iA}(y)\} \leq \alpha_i \text{ and } \min\{\nu_{iA}(x), \nu_{iA}(y)\} \geq \beta_i, \forall i, \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$\Rightarrow \mu_{iA}(xy^{-1}) \leq \max\{\mu_{iA}(x), \mu_{iA}(y)\} \leq \alpha_i \text{ and } \nu_{iA}(xy^{-1}) \geq \min\{\nu_{iA}(x), \nu_{iA}(y)\} \geq \beta_i, \forall i, \text{ since}$$

A is an intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy subgroup of a group G and by (1).

$$\Rightarrow \mu_{iA}(xy^{-1}) \leq \alpha_i \text{ and } \nu_{iA}(xy^{-1}) \geq \beta_i, \forall i.$$

$$\Rightarrow \mu_A(xy^{-1}) \leq \alpha \text{ and } \nu_A(xy^{-1}) \geq \beta$$

$$\Rightarrow xy^{-1} \in [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$$

$$\Rightarrow [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)} \text{ is a subgroup of } G.$$

Hence the Theorem.

3.4 Theorem

The IMFS A is an intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy subgroup of a group $G \Leftrightarrow$ each (α, β) -lower cut $[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ is a subgroup of G , $\forall \alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]^k$.

Proof From the above Theorem 3.3, it is clear.

3.5 Theorem

If A is an intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy normal subgroup of a group G and $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]^k$, then (α, β) -lower cut $[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ is a normal subgroup of G , where $\mu_A(e) \leq \alpha$, $\nu_A(e) \geq \beta$ and 'e' is the identity element of G .

Proof Let $x \in [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ and $g \in G$. Then $\mu_A(x) \leq \alpha$ and $\nu_A(x) \geq \beta$.

That is, $\mu_{iA}(x) \leq \alpha_i$ and $\nu_{iA}(x) \geq \beta_i \forall i \dots \dots \dots (1)$

Since A is an intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy normal subgroup of G ,

$$\begin{aligned} & \mu_{iA}(g^{-1}xg) = \mu_{iA}(x) \text{ and } \nu_{iA}(g^{-1}xg) = \nu_{iA}(x), \forall i. \\ & \Rightarrow \mu_{iA}(g^{-1}xg) = \mu_{iA}(x) \leq \alpha_i \text{ and } \nu_{iA}(g^{-1}xg) = \nu_{iA}(x) \geq \beta_i, \forall i, \text{ by using (1).} \\ & \Rightarrow \mu_{iA}(g^{-1}xg) \leq \alpha_i \text{ and } \nu_{iA}(g^{-1}xg) \geq \beta_i, \forall i. \\ & \Rightarrow \mu_A(g^{-1}xg) \leq \alpha \text{ and } \nu_A(g^{-1}xg) \geq \beta \\ & \Rightarrow g^{-1}xg \in [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)} \\ & \Rightarrow [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)} \text{ is a normal subgroup of } G. \end{aligned}$$

Hence the Theorem.

3.6 Theorem

If A is an intuitionistic multi-fuzzy subset of a group G , then A is an intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy subgroup of $G \Leftrightarrow$ each (α, β) -lower cut $[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ is a subgroup of G , for all $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]^k$ with $\alpha_i + \beta_i \leq 1, \forall i$.

Proof \Rightarrow Let A be an intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy subgroup of a group G . Then by the Theorem 3.4, each (α, β) -lower cut $[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ is a subgroup of G for all $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]^k$ with $\alpha_i + \beta_i \leq 1, \forall i$.

\Leftarrow Conversely, let A be an intuitionistic multi-fuzzy subset of a group G such that each (α, β) -lower cut $[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ is a subgroup of G for all $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]^k$ with $\alpha_i + \beta_i \leq 1, \forall i$.

To prove that A is an intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy subgroup of G , we prove :

- (i) $\mu_A(xy) \leq \max\{\mu_A(x), \mu_A(y)\}$ and $\nu_A(xy) \geq \min\{\nu_A(x), \nu_A(y)\}$ for all $x, y \in G$
- (ii) $\mu_A(x^{-1}) = \mu_A(x)$ and $\nu_A(x^{-1}) = \nu_A(x)$

For proof (i): Let $x, y \in G$ and for all i ,

$$\text{let } \alpha_i = \max\{\mu_{iA}(x), \mu_{iA}(y)\} \text{ and } \beta_i = \min\{\nu_{iA}(x), \nu_{iA}(y)\}.$$

Then $\forall i$, we have $\mu_{iA}(x) \leq \alpha_i, \mu_{iA}(y) \leq \alpha_i$ and $\nu_{iA}(x) \geq \beta_i, \nu_{iA}(y) \geq \beta_i$

That is, $\forall i$, we have $\mu_{iA}(x) \leq \alpha_i, \nu_{iA}(x) \geq \beta_i$ and $\mu_{iA}(y) \leq \alpha_i, \nu_{iA}(y) \geq \beta_i$

Then we have $\mu_A(x) \leq \alpha, \nu_A(x) \geq \beta$ and $\mu_A(y) \leq \alpha, \nu_A(y) \geq \beta$

That is, $x \in [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ and $y \in [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$

Therefore, $xy \in [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$, since each (α, β) -lower cut $[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ is a subgroup by hypothesis.

Therefore, $\forall i$, we have $\mu_{iA}(xy) \leq \alpha_i = \max\{\mu_{iA}(x), \mu_{iA}(y)\}$ and $\nu_{iA}(xy) \geq \beta_i = \min\{\nu_{iA}(x), \nu_{iA}(y)\}$.

That is, $\mu_A(xy) \leq \max\{\mu_A(x), \mu_A(y)\}$ and $\nu_A(xy) \geq \min\{\nu_A(x), \nu_A(y)\}$ and hence (i).

For proof (ii): Let $x \in G$ and $\forall i$, let $\mu_{iA}(x) = \alpha_i$ and $\nu_{iA}(x) = \beta_i$.

Then $\mu_{iA}(x) \leq \alpha_i$ and $\nu_{iA}(x) \geq \beta_i$ is true $\forall i$.

Therefore, $\mu_A(x) \leq \alpha$ and $\nu_A(x) \geq \beta$

Therefore, $x \in [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$.

Since each (α, β) -lower cut $[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ is a subgroup of G for all $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]^k$ and $x \in [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$, we have

$x^{-1} \in [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ which implies that $\mu_{iA}(x^{-1}) \leq \alpha_i$ and $\nu_{iA}(x^{-1}) \geq \beta_i$ is true $\forall i$.

$\Rightarrow \mu_{iA}(x^{-1}) \leq \mu_{iA}(x)$ and $\nu_{iA}(x^{-1}) \geq \nu_{iA}(x)$ is true $\forall i$.

Thus, $\forall i, \mu_{iA}(x) = \mu_{iA}((x^{-1})^{-1}) \leq \mu_{iA}(x^{-1}) \leq \mu_{iA}(x)$ which implies that $\mu_{iA}(x^{-1}) = \mu_{iA}(x), \forall i$ and hence $\mu_A(x^{-1}) = \mu_A(x)$.

And $\forall i, v_{iA}(x) = v_{iA}((x^{-1})^{-1}) \geq v_{iA}(x^{-1}) \geq v_{iA}(x)$ which implies that $v_{iA}(x^{-1}) = v_{iA}(x), \forall i$ and hence $v_A(x^{-1}) = v_A(x)$.

Hence A is an intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy subgroup of G and hence the Theorem.

3.7 Theorem

If A and B are any two intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy subgroups (IMAFSG's) of a group G, then $(A \cup B)$ is an intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy subgroup of G.

Proof since A and B are IMAFSG's of G, we have $\forall x, y \in G$,

- (i) $\mu_A(xy^{-1}) \leq \max\{\mu_A(x), \mu_A(y)\}$ and $v_A(xy^{-1}) \geq \min\{v_A(x), v_A(y)\}$
- (ii) $\mu_B(xy^{-1}) \leq \max\{\mu_B(x), \mu_B(y)\}$ and $v_B(xy^{-1}) \geq \min\{v_B(x), v_B(y)\}$ (1)

Now $A \cup B = \{ \langle x, \mu_{A \cup B}(x), v_{A \cup B}(x) \rangle : x \in G \}$ where $\mu_{A \cup B}(x) = \max\{ \mu_A(x), \mu_B(x) \}$ and $v_{A \cup B}(x) = \min\{ v_A(x), v_B(x) \}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Then } \mu_{A \cup B}(xy^{-1}) &= \max\{ \mu_A(xy^{-1}), \mu_B(xy^{-1}) \} \\ &\leq \max\{ \max\{\mu_A(x), \mu_A(y)\}, \max\{\mu_B(x), \mu_B(y)\} \}, \text{ by using (1)} \\ &= \max\{ \max\{\mu_A(x), \mu_B(x)\}, \max\{\mu_A(y), \mu_B(y)\} \} \\ &= \max\{ \mu_{A \cup B}(x), \mu_{A \cup B}(y) \} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and } v_{A \cup B}(xy^{-1}) &= \min\{ v_A(xy^{-1}), v_B(xy^{-1}) \} \\ &\geq \min\{ \min\{v_A(x), v_A(y)\}, \min\{v_B(x), v_B(y)\} \}, \text{ by using (1)} \\ &= \min\{ \min\{v_A(x), v_B(x)\}, \min\{v_A(y), v_B(y)\} \} \\ &= \min\{ v_{A \cup B}(x), v_{A \cup B}(y) \} \end{aligned}$$

That is, $\mu_{A \cup B}(xy^{-1}) \leq \max\{ \mu_{A \cup B}(x), \mu_{A \cup B}(y) \}$ and $v_{A \cup B}(xy^{-1}) \geq \min\{ v_{A \cup B}(x), v_{A \cup B}(y) \}$, $\forall x, y \in G$.

Hence $(A \cup B)$ is an intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy subgroup of G.

Hence the Theorem.

3.8 Theorem

The intersection of any two IMAFSG's of a group G need not be an IMAFSG of G.

Proof Consider the abelian group $G = \{ e, a, b, ab \}$ with usual multiplication such that $a^2 = e = b^2$ and $ab = ba$. Let $A = \{ \langle e, (0.2, 0.2), (0.7, 0.8) \rangle, \langle a, (0.5, 0.5), (0.4, 0.4) \rangle, \langle b, (0.5, 0.5), (0.2, 0.4) \rangle, \langle ab, (0.4, 0.5), (0.2, 0.4) \rangle \}$ and $B = \{ \langle e, (0.3, 0.1), (0.7, 0.8) \rangle, \langle a, (0.8, 0.4), (0.2, 0.6) \rangle, \langle b, (0.6, 0.4), (0.4, 0.5) \rangle, \langle ab, (0.8, 0.4), (0.2, 0.5) \rangle \}$ be two IMFS's having dimension two of the group G. Clearly A and B are IMAFSG's of G.

Then $A \cap B = \{ \langle e, (0.2, 0.1), (0.7, 0.8) \rangle, \langle a, (0.5, 0.4), (0.4, 0.6) \rangle, \langle b, (0.5, 0.4), (0.4, 0.5) \rangle, \langle ab, (0.4, 0.4), (0.2, 0.5) \rangle \}$. Here, it is easily verify that $A \cap B$ is not an IMAFSG of G. Hence the Theorem.

3.9 Theorem

Let A and B be an IMAFSG's of a group G. But it is an uncertain to verify that $A \cap B$ is an IMAFSG of G.

Proof This proof is done by the following two examples that are discussed in two cases : case(i) and case(ii).

Case (i) : A and B are IMAFSG's of a group $G \Rightarrow A \cup B$ is an IMAFSG of G but $A \cap B$ is not an IMAFSG of the group G.

Consider the abelian group $G = \{ e, a, b, ab \}$ with usual multiplication such that $a^2 = e = b^2$ and $ab = ba$. Let $A = \{ \langle e, (0.2, 0.2), (0.7, 0.8) \rangle, \langle a, (0.5, 0.5), (0.4, 0.4) \rangle, \langle b, (0.5, 0.5), (0.2, 0.4) \rangle, \langle ab, (0.4, 0.5), (0.2, 0.4) \rangle \}$ and $B = \{ \langle e, (0.3, 0.1), (0.7, 0.8) \rangle, \langle a, (0.8, 0.4), (0.2, 0.6) \rangle, \langle b, (0.6, 0.4), (0.4, 0.5) \rangle, \langle ab, (0.8, 0.4), (0.2, 0.5) \rangle \}$ be two IMFS's having dimension two of the group G. Clearly A and B are IMAFSG's of G.

Then $A \cup B = \{ \langle e, (0.3, 0.2), (0.7, 0.8) \rangle, \langle a, (0.8, 0.5), (0.2, 0.4) \rangle, \langle b, (0.6, 0.5), (0.2, 0.4) \rangle, \langle ab, (0.8, 0.5), (0.2, 0.4) \rangle \}$ and $A \cap B = \{ \langle e, (0.2, 0.1), (0.7, 0.8) \rangle, \langle a, (0.5, 0.4), (0.4, 0.6) \rangle, \langle b, (0.5, 0.4), (0.4, 0.5) \rangle, \langle ab, (0.4, 0.4), (0.2, 0.5) \rangle \}$.

Here, it is easily verify that $A \cup B$ is an IMAFSG of G but $A \cap B$ is not an IMAFSG of G. Hence case (i).

Case (ii) : A and B are IMAFSG's of a group $G \Rightarrow$ both $A \cup B$ and $A \cap B$ are IMAFSG's of the group G.

Consider the abelian group $G = \{ e, a, b, ab \}$ with usual multiplication such that $a^2 = e = b^2$ and $ab = ba$. Let $A = \{ \langle e, (0.2, 0.1), (0.8, 0.8) \rangle, \langle a, (0.5, 0.4), (0.4, 0.6) \rangle, \langle b, (0.5, 0.4), (0.4, 0.5) \rangle, \langle ab, (0.5, 0.4), (0.4, 0.5) \rangle \}$ and $B = \{ \langle e, (0.3, 0.2), (0.7, 0.7) \rangle, \langle a, (0.8, 0.5), (0.2, 0.4) \rangle, \langle b, (0.6, 0.5), (0.4, 0.2) \rangle, \langle ab, (0.8, 0.4), (0.2, 0.2) \rangle \}$ be two IMFS's having dimension two of the group G. Clearly A and B are IMAFSG's of G.

Then $A \cup B = \{ \langle e, (0.3, 0.2), (0.7, 0.7) \rangle, \langle a, (0.8, 0.5), (0.2, 0.4) \rangle, \langle b, (0.6, 0.5), (0.4, 0.2) \rangle, \langle ab, (0.8, 0.4), (0.2, 0.2) \rangle \}$ and $A \cap B = \{ \langle e, (0.2, 0.1), (0.8, 0.8) \rangle, \langle a, (0.5, 0.4), (0.4, 0.6) \rangle, \langle b, (0.5, 0.4), (0.4, 0.5) \rangle, \langle ab, (0.5, 0.4), (0.4, 0.5) \rangle \}$.

Here, it is easily to verify that both $A \cup B$ and $A \cap B$ are IMAFSG's of G. Hence case (ii).

From case (i) and case (ii), clearly it is an uncertain to verify that $A \cap B$ is an IMAFSG of G.

Hence the Theorem.

3.10 Theorem

Let A and B be any two IMAFSG's of a group G. Then $A \circ B$ is an IMAFSG of G $\Leftrightarrow A \circ B = B \circ A$

Proof Since A and B are IMAFSG's of G, each (α, β) -lower cuts $[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ and $[B]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ are subgroups of G, $\forall \alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]^k$ with $\alpha_i + \beta_i \leq 1, \forall i$ (1)

Suppose $A \circ B$ is an IMAFSG of G.

\Leftrightarrow each (α, β) -lower cuts $[A \circ B]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ are subgroups of G , $\forall \alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]^k$ with $\alpha_i + \beta_i \leq 1, \forall i$.

Now, from (1), $[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)} [B]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ is a subgroup of $G \Leftrightarrow [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)} [B]_{(\alpha, \beta)} = [B]_{(\alpha, \beta)} [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$, since if H and K are any two subgroups of G , then HK is a subgroup of $G \Leftrightarrow HK=KH$.

$$\begin{aligned} &\Leftrightarrow [A \circ B]_{(\alpha, \beta)} = [B \circ A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}, \forall \alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]^k \text{ with } \alpha_i + \beta_i \leq 1, \forall i. \\ &\Leftrightarrow A \circ B = B \circ A \end{aligned}$$

Hence the Theorem.

3.11 Theorem

If A is any IMAFSG of a group G , then $A \circ A = A$.

Proof Since A is an IMAFSG of a group G ,

each (α, β) -lower cut $[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ is a subgroup of G , $\forall \alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]^k$ with $\alpha_i + \beta_i \leq 1, \forall i$.

$\Rightarrow [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)} [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)} = [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$, since H is a subgroup of $G \Rightarrow HH = H$.

$\Rightarrow [A \circ A]_{(\alpha, \beta)} = [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}, \forall \alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]^k$ with $\alpha_i + \beta_i \leq 1, \forall i$.

$\Rightarrow A \circ A = A$

Hence the Theorem.

4. INTUITIONISTIC MULTI-FUZZY COSETS

In this section we shall prove some theorems on intuitionistic multi-fuzzy cosets of a group G .

4.1 Definition

Let G be a group and A be an IMAFSG of G . Let $x \in G$ be a fixed element. Then the set $xA = \{ (g, \mu_{xA}(g), \nu_{xA}(g)) : g \in G \}$ where $\mu_{xA}(g) = \mu_A(x^{-1}g)$ and $\nu_{xA}(g) = \nu_A(x^{-1}g), \forall g \in G$ is called the intuitionistic multi-fuzzy left coset of G determined by A and x .

Similarly, the set $Ax = \{ (g, \mu_{Ax}(g), \nu_{Ax}(g)) : g \in G \}$ where $\mu_{Ax}(g) = \mu_A(gx^{-1})$ and $\nu_{Ax}(g) = \nu_A(gx^{-1}), \forall g \in G$ is called the intuitionistic multi-fuzzy right coset of G determined by A and x .

4.2 Remark

It is clear that if A is an intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy normal subgroup of G , then the intuitionistic multi-fuzzy left coset and the intuitionistic multi-fuzzy right coset of A on G coincides and in this case, we simply call it as intuitionistic multi-fuzzy coset.

4.3 Example

Let G be a group. Then $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle, x \in G / \mu_A(x) = \mu_A(e) \text{ and } \nu_A(x) = \nu_A(e) \}$ is an

intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy normal subgroup of G.

Proof It is easy to verify.

4.4 Theorem

Let A be an intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy subgroup of a group G and x be any fixed element of G. Then the following are holds :

- (i) $x[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)} = [xA]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$
- (ii) $[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}x = [Ax]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$, $\forall \alpha, \beta \in [0,1]^k$ with $\alpha_i + \beta_i \leq 1$, $\forall i$.

Proof For proof (i),

Now $[xA]_{(\alpha, \beta)} = \{ g \in G : \mu_{xA}(g) \leq \alpha \text{ and } \nu_{xA}(g) \geq \beta \}$ with $\alpha_i + \beta_i \leq 1$, $\forall i$.

Also $x[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)} = x \{ y \in G : \mu_A(y) \leq \alpha \text{ and } \nu_A(y) \geq \beta \}$
 $= \{ xy \in G : \mu_A(y) \leq \alpha \text{ and } \nu_A(y) \geq \beta \}$ (1)

put $xy = g \Rightarrow y = x^{-1}g$. Then (1) becomes as,

$x[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)} = \{ g \in G : \mu_A(x^{-1}g) \leq \alpha \text{ and } \nu_A(x^{-1}g) \geq \beta \}$
 $= \{ g \in G : \mu_{xA}(g) \leq \alpha \text{ and } \nu_{xA}(g) \geq \beta \}$
 $= [xA]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$

Therefore, $x[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)} = [xA]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$, $\forall \alpha, \beta \in [0,1]^k$ with $\alpha_i + \beta_i \leq 1$, $\forall i$.

Hence the proof (i).

For proof (ii),

Now $[Ax]_{(\alpha, \beta)} = \{ g \in G : \mu_{Ax}(g) \leq \alpha \text{ and } \nu_{Ax}(g) \geq \beta \}$ with $\alpha_i + \beta_i \leq 1$, $\forall i$.

Also $[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}x = \{ y \in G : \mu_A(y) \leq \alpha \text{ and } \nu_A(y) \geq \beta \}x$
 $= \{ yx \in G : \mu_A(y) \leq \alpha \text{ and } \nu_A(y) \geq \beta \}$ (2)

put $yx = g \Rightarrow y = gx^{-1}$. Then (2) becomes as,

$[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}x = \{ g \in G : \mu_A(gx^{-1}) \leq \alpha \text{ and } \nu_A(gx^{-1}) \geq \beta \}$
 $= \{ g \in G : \mu_{Ax}(g) \leq \alpha \text{ and } \nu_{Ax}(g) \geq \beta \}$
 $= [Ax]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$

Therefore, $[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}x = [Ax]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$, $\forall \alpha, \beta \in [0,1]^k$ with $\alpha_i + \beta_i \leq 1$, $\forall i$.

Hence the proof (ii) and hence the Theorem.

4.5 Theorem

Let A be an intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy subgroup of a group G. Let x,y be any two elements of G such that $\alpha = \max\{ \mu_A(x), \mu_A(y) \}$ and $\beta = \min\{ \nu_A(x), \nu_A(y) \}$. Then the

following are holds :

- (i) $xA = yA \Leftrightarrow x^{-1}y \in [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$
- (ii) $Ax = Ay \Leftrightarrow xy^{-1} \in [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$
- (iii)

Proof For (i), Now $xA = yA \Leftrightarrow [xA]_{(\alpha, \beta)} = [yA]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$, $\forall \alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]^k$ with $\alpha_i + \beta_i \leq 1, \forall i$.

$$\Leftrightarrow x[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)} = y[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}, \text{by Theorem 4.4(i).}$$

$\Leftrightarrow x^{-1}y \in [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$, since each (α, β) -lower cut $[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ is a subgroup of G. Hence the proof (i).

For (ii), Now $Ax = Ay \Leftrightarrow [Ax]_{(\alpha, \beta)} = [Ay]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$, $\forall \alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]^k$ with $\alpha_i + \beta_i \leq 1, \forall i$.

$$\Leftrightarrow [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}x = [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}y, \text{by Theorem 4.4(ii).}$$

$\Leftrightarrow xy^{-1} \in [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$, since each (α, β) -lower cut $[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ is a subgroup of G. Hence the proof (ii) and hence the Theorem.

5. HOMOMORPHISM OF INTUITIONISTIC MULTI-ANTI FUZZY SUBGROUPS

In this section we shall prove some theorems on intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy subgroups of a group with the help of a homomorphism.

5.1 Proposition

Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be an onto map. If A and B are intuitionistic multi-fuzzy sets having the dimension k of X and Y respectively, then for each (α, β) -lower cuts $[A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ and $[B]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$, the following are holds :

- (i) $f([A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}) \subseteq [f(A)]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$
- (ii) $f^{-1}([B]_{(\alpha, \beta)}) = [f^{-1}(B)]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$, $\forall \alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]^k$ with $\alpha_i + \beta_i \leq 1, \forall i$.

Proof For (i), Let $y \in f([A]_{(\alpha, \beta)})$.

Then there exists an element $x \in [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ such that $f(x) = y$.

Then we have $\mu_A(x) \leq \alpha$ and $\nu_A(x) \geq \beta$, since $x \in [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$.

$$\begin{aligned} &\Rightarrow \mu_{iA}(x) \leq \alpha_i \text{ and } \nu_{iA}(x) \geq \beta_i, \forall i. \\ &\Rightarrow \min\{\mu_{iA}(x) : x \in f^{-1}(y)\} \leq \alpha_i \text{ and } \max\{\nu_{iA}(x) : x \in f^{-1}(y)\} \geq \beta_i, \forall i. \\ &\Rightarrow \min\{\mu_A(x) : x \in f^{-1}(y)\} \leq \alpha \text{ and } \max\{\nu_A(x) : x \in f^{-1}(y)\} \geq \beta \\ &\Rightarrow \mu_{f(A)}(y) \leq \alpha \text{ and } \nu_{f(A)}(y) \geq \beta \\ &\Rightarrow y \in [f(A)]_{(\alpha, \beta)} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $f([A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}) \subseteq [f(A)]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$, $\forall A \in \text{IMFS}(X)$. Hence the proof (i).

For the proof (ii),

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Let } x \in [f^{-1}(B)]_{(\alpha, \beta)} &\Leftrightarrow \{x \in X : \mu_{f^{-1}(B)}(x) \leq \alpha, \nu_{f^{-1}(B)}(x) \geq \beta\} \\ &\Leftrightarrow \{x \in X : \mu_{if^{-1}(B)}(x) \leq \alpha_i, \nu_{if^{-1}(B)}(x) \geq \beta_i\}, \forall i. \\ &\Leftrightarrow \{x \in X : \mu_{iB}(f(x)) \leq \alpha_i, \nu_{iB}(f(x)) \geq \beta_i\}, \forall i. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\Leftrightarrow \{x \in X : \mu_B(f(x)) \leq \alpha, \nu_B(f(x)) \geq \beta\} \\ &\Leftrightarrow \{x \in X : f(x) \in [B]_{(\alpha, \beta)}\} \\ &\Leftrightarrow \{x \in X : x \in f^{-1}([B]_{(\alpha, \beta)})\} \\ &\Leftrightarrow f^{-1}([B]_{(\alpha, \beta)}) \end{aligned}$$

Hence the proof (ii).

5.2 Theorem

Let $f : G_1 \rightarrow G_2$ be an onto homomorphism and if A is an IMAFSG of group G_1 , then $f(A)$ is an IMAFSG of group G_2 .

Proof By Theorem 3.6, it is enough to prove that each (α, β) -lower cuts $[f(A)]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ is a subgroup of G_2 for all $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]^k$ with $\alpha_i + \beta_i \leq 1, \forall i$.

Let $y_1, y_2 \in [f(A)]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$. Then $\mu_{f(A)}(y_1) \leq \alpha, \nu_{f(A)}(y_1) \geq \beta$ and $\mu_{f(A)}(y_2) \leq \alpha, \nu_{f(A)}(y_2) \geq \beta$
 $\Rightarrow \mu_{if(A)}(y_1) \leq \alpha_i, \nu_{if(A)}(y_1) \geq \beta_i$ and $\mu_{if(A)}(y_2) \leq \alpha_i, \nu_{if(A)}(y_2) \geq \beta_i, \forall i. \dots\dots\dots(1)$

By the proposition 5.1(i), we have $f([A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}) \subseteq [f(A)]_{(\alpha, \beta)}, \forall A \in \text{IMFS}(G_1)$

Since f is onto, there exists some x_1 and x_2 in G_1 such that $f(x_1) = y_1$ and $f(x_2) = y_2$.
 Therefore, (1) becomes as,

$$\mu_{if(A)}(f(x_1)) \leq \alpha_i, \nu_{if(A)}(f(x_1)) \geq \beta_i \text{ and } \mu_{if(A)}(f(x_2)) \leq \alpha_i, \nu_{if(A)}(f(x_2)) \geq \beta_i, \forall i.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \mu_{iA}(x_1) \leq \mu_{if(A)}(f(x_1)) \leq \alpha_i, \nu_{iA}(x_1) \geq \nu_{if(A)}(f(x_1)) \geq \beta_i \text{ and} \\ \mu_{iA}(x_2) \leq \mu_{if(A)}(f(x_2)) \leq \alpha_i, \nu_{iA}(x_2) \geq \nu_{if(A)}(f(x_2)) \geq \beta_i, \forall i. \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow \mu_{iA}(x_1) \leq \alpha_i, \nu_{iA}(x_1) \geq \beta_i \text{ and } \mu_{iA}(x_2) \leq \alpha_i, \nu_{iA}(x_2) \geq \beta_i, \forall i.$$

$$\Rightarrow \mu_A(x_1) \leq \alpha, \nu_A(x_1) \geq \beta \text{ and } \mu_A(x_2) \leq \alpha, \nu_A(x_2) \geq \beta$$

$$\Rightarrow \max\{\mu_A(x_1), \mu_A(x_2)\} \leq \alpha \text{ and } \min\{\nu_A(x_1), \nu_A(x_2)\} \geq \beta$$

$$\Rightarrow \mu_A(x_1 x_2^{-1}) \leq \max\{\mu_A(x_1), \mu_A(x_2)\} \leq \alpha \text{ and } \nu_A(x_1 x_2^{-1}) \geq \min\{\nu_A(x_1), \nu_A(x_2)\} \geq \beta, \text{ since } A \in \text{IMAFSG}(G_1).$$

$$\Rightarrow \mu_A(x_1 x_2^{-1}) \leq \alpha \text{ and } \nu_A(x_1 x_2^{-1}) \geq \beta$$

$$\Rightarrow x_1 x_2^{-1} \in [A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$$

$$\Rightarrow f(x_1 x_2^{-1}) \in f([A]_{(\alpha, \beta)}) \subseteq [f(A)]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$$

$$\Rightarrow f(x_1) f(x_2^{-1}) \in [f(A)]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$$

$$\Rightarrow f(x_1) f(x_2)^{-1} \in [f(A)]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$$

$$\Rightarrow y_1 y_2^{-1} \in [f(A)]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$$

$$\Rightarrow [f(A)]_{(\alpha, \beta)} \text{ is a subgroup of } G_2, \forall \alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]^k.$$

$\Rightarrow f(A) \in \text{IMAFSG}(G_2)$

Hence the Theorem.

5.3 Corollary

If $f : G_1 \rightarrow G_2$ be a homomorphism of a group G_1 onto a group G_2 and $\{ A_i : i \in I \}$ be a family of IMAFSG's of group G_1 , then $f(\cup A_i)$ is an IMAFSG of group G_2 .

5.4 Theorem

Let $f : G_1 \rightarrow G_2$ be a homomorphism of a group G_1 into a group G_2 . If B is an IMAFSG of G_2 , then $f^{-1}(B)$ is also an IMAFSG of G_1 .

Proof By Theorem 3.6, it is enough to prove that each (α, β) -lower cuts $[f^{-1}(B)]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$ is a subgroup of $G_1, \forall \alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]^k$ with $\alpha_i + \beta_i \leq 1, \forall i$.

Let $x_1, x_2 \in [f^{-1}(B)]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$. Then it implies that

$$\mu_{f^{-1}(B)}(x_1) \leq \alpha, \nu_{f^{-1}(B)}(x_1) \geq \beta \text{ and } \mu_{f^{-1}(B)}(x_2) \leq \alpha, \nu_{f^{-1}(B)}(x_2) \geq \beta.$$

$$\Rightarrow \mu_B(f(x_1)) \leq \alpha, \nu_B(f(x_1)) \geq \beta \text{ and } \mu_B(f(x_2)) \leq \alpha, \nu_B(f(x_2)) \geq \beta.$$

$$\Rightarrow \max\{ \mu_B(f(x_1)), \mu_B(f(x_2)) \} \leq \alpha \text{ and } \min\{ \nu_B(f(x_1)), \nu_B(f(x_2)) \} \geq \beta.$$

$$\Rightarrow \mu_B(f(x_1)f(x_2)^{-1}) \leq \max\{ \mu_B(f(x_1)), \mu_B(f(x_2)) \} \leq \alpha \text{ and } \nu_B(f(x_1)f(x_2)^{-1}) \geq \min\{ \nu_B(f(x_1)), \nu_B(f(x_2)) \} \geq \beta, \text{ since } B \in \text{IMAFSG}(G_2).$$

$$\Rightarrow f(x_1)f(x_2)^{-1} \in [B]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$$

$$\Rightarrow f(x_1x_2^{-1}) \in [B]_{(\alpha, \beta)}, \text{ since } f \text{ is a homomorphism.}$$

$$\Rightarrow x_1x_2^{-1} \in f^{-1}([B]_{(\alpha, \beta)}) = [f^{-1}(B)]_{(\alpha, \beta)}, \text{ by the proposition 5.1(ii).}$$

$$\Rightarrow x_1x_2^{-1} \in [f^{-1}(B)]_{(\alpha, \beta)}$$

$$\Rightarrow [f^{-1}(B)]_{(\alpha, \beta)} \text{ is a subgroup of } G_1$$

$$\Rightarrow f^{-1}(B) \text{ is an IMAFSG of } G_1.$$

Hence the Theorem.

5.5 Theorem

Let $f : G_1 \rightarrow G_2$ be a surjective homomorphism and if A is an IMAFNSG of group G_1 , then $f(A)$ is also an IMAFNSG of group G_2 .

Proof Let $g_2 \in G_2$ and $y \in f(A)$.

Since f is surjective,

there exists $g_1 \in G_1$ and $x \in A$ such that $f(x) = y$ and $f(g_1) = g_2$.

Since A is an IMAFNSG of G_1 ,

$$\mu_A(g_1^{-1}xg_1) = \mu_A(x) \quad \text{and} \quad \nu_A(g_1^{-1}xg_1) = \nu_A(x), \forall x \in A \text{ and } g_1 \in G_1.$$

Now consider, $\mu_{f(A)}(g_2^{-1}yg_2) = \mu_{f(A)}(f(g_1^{-1}xg_1))$, since f is a homomorphism.

$$\begin{aligned} &= \mu_{f(A)}(y'), \text{ where } y' = f(g_1^{-1}xg_1) = g_2^{-1}yg_2 \\ &= \min\{ \mu_A(x') : f(x') = y \text{ for } x' \in G_1 \} \\ &= \min\{ \mu_A(x') : f(x') = f(g_1^{-1}xg_1) \text{ for } x' \in G_1 \} \\ &= \min\{ \mu_A(g_1^{-1}xg_1) : f(g_1^{-1}xg_1) = y' = g_2^{-1}yg_2 \text{ for } x \in A, g_1 \in G_1 \} \\ &= \min\{ \mu_A(x) : f(g_1^{-1}xg_1) = g_2^{-1}yg_2 \text{ for } x \in A, g_1 \in G_1 \} \\ &= \min\{ \mu_A(x) : f(g_1)^{-1}f(x)f(g_1) = g_2^{-1}yg_2 \text{ for } x \in A, g_1 \in G_1 \} \\ &= \min\{ \mu_A(x) : g_2^{-1}f(x)g_2 = g_2^{-1}yg_2 \text{ for } x \in G_1 \} \\ &= \min\{ \mu_A(x) : f(x) = y \text{ for } x \in G_1 \} \\ &= \mu_{f(A)}(y) \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we can easily prove that $\nu_{f(A)}(g_2^{-1}yg_2) = \nu_{f(A)}(y)$.

Hence $f(A)$ is an IMAFNSG of G_2 and hence the Theorem.

5.6 Theorem

If A is an IMAFNSG of a group G , then there exists a natural homomorphism $f : G \rightarrow G/A$ is defined by $f(x) = xA$, $\forall x \in G$.

Proof Let $f : G \rightarrow G/A$ be defined by $f(x) = xA$, $\forall x \in G$.

Claim1: f is a homomorphism

That is, to prove: $f(xy) = f(x)f(y)$, $\forall x, y \in G$.

That is, to prove: $(xy)A = (xA)(yA)$, $\forall x, y \in G$.

Since A is an IMAFNSG of G , we have $\mu_A(g^{-1}xg) = \mu_A(x)$ and $\nu_A(g^{-1}xg) = \nu_A(x)$, $\forall x \in A$ and $g \in G$.

Or, equivalently, $\mu_A(xy) = \mu_A(yx)$ and $\nu_A(xy) = \nu_A(yx)$, $\forall x, y \in G$.

Also, $\forall g \in G$, we have

$$(xA)(g) = (\mu_{xA}(g), \nu_{xA}(g)) = (\mu_A(x^{-1}g), \nu_A(x^{-1}g))$$

$$(yA)(g) = (\mu_{yA}(g), \nu_{yA}(g)) = (\mu_A(y^{-1}g), \nu_A(y^{-1}g))$$

$$[(xy)A](g) = (\mu_{(xy)A}(g), \nu_{(xy)A}(g)) = (\mu_A[(xy)^{-1}g], \nu_A[(xy)^{-1}g])$$

$\forall g \in G$, by definition 2.16, we have

$$[(xA)(yA)](g) = (\max[\min\{\mu_{xA}(r), \mu_{yA}(s)\} : g = rs], \min[\max\{\nu_{xA}(r), \nu_{yA}(s)\} : g = rs])$$

$$= (\max[\min\{\mu_A(x^{-1}r), \mu_A(y^{-1}s)\} : g = rs], \min[\max\{\nu_A(x^{-1}r), \nu_A(y^{-1}s)\} : g = rs])$$

Claim2: $\mu_A[(xy)^{-1}g] = \max[\min\{\mu_A(x^{-1}r), \mu_A(y^{-1}s)\} : g = rs]$ and
 $\nu_A[(xy)^{-1}g] = \min[\max\{\nu_A(x^{-1}r), \nu_A(y^{-1}s)\} : g = rs], \forall g \in G.$

Now consider $\mu_A[(xy)^{-1}g] = \mu_A[y^{-1}x^{-1}g]$

$$= \mu_A[y^{-1}x^{-1}rs], \text{ since } g = rs.$$

$$= \mu_A[y^{-1}(x^{-1}rsy^{-1})y]$$

$$= \mu_A[x^{-1}rsy^{-1}], \text{ since } A \text{ is normal.}$$

$$\leq \max\{\mu_A(x^{-1}r), \mu_A(sy^{-1})\}, \text{ since } A \text{ is IMAFSG of } G.$$

$$= \max\{\mu_A(x^{-1}r), \mu_A(y^{-1}s)\}, \forall g = rs \in G, \text{ since } A \text{ is normal}$$

Therefore, $\mu_A[(xy)^{-1}g] = \min[\max\{\mu_A(x^{-1}r), \mu_A(y^{-1}s)\} : g = rs], \forall g \in G.$
 $= \max[\min\{\mu_A(x^{-1}r), \mu_A(y^{-1}s)\} : g = rs], \forall g \in G.$

Similarly, we can easily prove $\nu_A[(xy)^{-1}g] = \min[\max\{\nu_A(x^{-1}r), \nu_A(y^{-1}s)\} : g = rs], \forall g \in G.$
Hence the claim2.

Thus, $[(xy)A](g) = [(xA)(yA)](g), \forall g \in G.$

$$\Rightarrow (xy)A = (xA)(yA)$$

$$\Rightarrow f(xy) = f(x)f(y)$$

$\Rightarrow f$ is a homomorphism

Hence the claim1 and hence the Theorem.

6. CONCLUSION

In the theory of fuzzy sets, the level subsets are vital role for its development. Similarly, the (α, β) -lower cut of an intuitionistic multi-fuzzy sets are very important role for the development of the theory of intuitionistic multi-fuzzy sets. In this paper an attempt has been made to study some algebraic natures of intuitionistic multi-anti fuzzy subgroups and their properties with the help of their (α, β) -lower cut sets.

REFERENCES

- [1] Atanassov K.T., Intuitionistic fuzzy sets, Fuzzy Sets and Systems, 20(1986), no.1, 87-96.
- [2] Basnet D.K. and Sarma N.K., A note on Intuitionistic Fuzzy Equivalence Relation, International Mathematical Forum, 5, 2010, no.67, 3301-3307.
- [3] Biswas R., Vague Groups, International Journal of Computational Cognition, Vol.4, no.2, June 2006.
- [4] Das P.S., Fuzzy groups and level subgroups, Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications, 84 (1981), 264-269.
- [5] Kul Hur and Su Youn Jang, The lattice of Intuitionistic fuzzy congruences, International Mathematical Forum, 1, 2006, no.5, 211-236.
- [6] Mukharjee N.P. and Bhattacharya P., Fuzzy normal subgroups and fuzzy cosets, Information Sciences, 34 (1984), 225-239.

- [7] Muthuraj R. and Balamurugan S., Multi-Anti fuzzy group and its Lower level subgroups, International Journal of Engineering Research and Applications, Vol.3, Issue 6, Nov-Dec 2013, pp.1498-1501.
- [8] Rosenfeld A., Fuzzy groups, Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications, 35 (1971), 512-517.
- [9] Sabu S. and Ramakrishnan T.V., Multi-fuzzy sets, International Mathematical Forum, 50 (2010), 2471-2476.
- [10] Sabu S. and Ramakrishnan T.V., Multi-fuzzy topology, International Journal of Applied Mathematics (accepted).
- [11] Sabu S. and Ramakrishnan T.V., Multi-fuzzy subgroups, Int. J. Contemp. Math.Sciences, Vol.6, 8 (2011), 365-372.
- [12] Sharma P.K., Intuitionistic Fuzzy Groups, ifrsa International Journal of Data warehousing and Mining, vol.1, 2011, iss.1, 86-94.
- [13] Shinoj T.K. and Sunil Jacob John , Intuitionistic Fuzzy Multisets, International Journal of Engineering Science and Innovative Technology, Vol.2, 2013, Issue 6, 1-24.
- [14] Zadeh L.A., Fuzzy Sets, Information and Control 8, (1965), 338-353.